

Machine Learning and Assessment: Political Barrier to its Implementation in Educational Policy, Research and Practice in Nigeria University

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Abstract

The paper examined machine learning and assessment: political barrier to its implementation in educational policy, research and practice in Nigeria University. The paper adopted analytical method because several articles, journals and literatures related machine learning and assessment were reviewed. The aim of machines learning in assessment is to perform cognitive functions in a manner associated with the human's mind. It powers feedback and also helps students identify areas for improvement on their own. This growth has not only led to improvements in students' proficiency in traditional core abilities but has also contributed to development in the emerging construction of 21st century skills. These key transformations witnessed in the realm of technical advancement in statistical method within academic related literature in the area of adaptive learning, predictive analytic and personalized learning automated grading system and the political obstacles to its implementation was discussed. This research also suggested that teachers should be included as significant stakeholders for formulating and implementing educational policies considering that they play a crucial role in converting policy on education documents into practical use. Machine learning and assessment as an emerging aspect of educational assessment provides significant diagnostic feedback should be incorporated into educational policy in the country.

Keywords: Assessment, Predictive Analytics, Machine learning, Political Barriers, Implementation,

Introduction

In education, assessment refers to the extensive variety of methods or tools that educators use to evaluate, measure, and document the academic readiness, learning progress, skill, or educational needs of students. It is used to identify individual student weaknesses and strengths so that educators can provide specialized academic support, or social services. Assessment is one of the

Received: 23 January 2025

Revised: 02 February 2025

Accepted: 11 February 2025

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DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.14852631](https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.14852631)

methods used in ascertaining or finding out how well students have performed during teaching and after teaching-learning process. Assessment is a technique used for collecting data on behaviour of individuals. It involves fact finding activity and, also enable teachers describe the prevailing status of the learner within the context of a given educational objective (Nna-kue & Anunaobi, 2023). Assessment is also defined as the process of organizing measurement data and fashioning them in an interpretable manner on the basis of which judgement could be made. That is, it involves fact finding activity and enables the assessor describe the prevailing status of the learner within the context of a given educational objective (Asuru, 2015).

However, the developing technology has widely impacted on how assessments can be planned and administered online. The traditional paper-and pencil tests are becoming outdated as assessments are now being designed adapted and delivered online using interactive tasks and simulations (Gierl & Haladyna, 2012). Educational Testing Services (ETS) have conducted significant research on scoring written content over the past years by utilizing natural language processing techniques with major human efforts in machine learning techniques, which needs less human intervention. The Educational Testing Services (ETS) work include automated scoring of formative assessment of scientific argumentation ((Mao, Liu, Roohr, Belur, Mulholand, Lee & Pallant, 2018), Neural networks for short answer scoring (Riordan, Horbach, Cahill, Zesch & Lee, 2017) and automatically scoring tests of proficiency in music instruction (Madnani, Cahill & Riordan, 2016). These have been an important development as short answer questions have been recognized as a tool to perform a deeper assessment of the students' knowledge than multiple choice questions. Again, online delivery of assessments clearly create potential for more efficient and effective delivery, analysis and reporting of assessments which have the capacity to accelerate improvement in students' learning by providing actionable information to teachers in a timely manner.

Moreso, newer models of assessment have also emerged that provide greater insight to examiners. For example, cognitive diagnostic assessment (CDA) is relatively new development in educational measurement which helps assessment researchers examine test takers' mastery of specific skills much greater than traditional models. This can be useful for providing much more fine-grained diagnostic information about test takers' degree of mastery of various defined skills (Lee & Sawaki, 2019). Whilst CDA development was largely motivated by the need for new formative assessment methods, the technique has been retrofitted to norm-referenced tests (Jang, 2018). It should be noted that in other developing countries cognitive diagnostic assessment (CDA) is an emerging aspect of educational measurement and evaluation that yield rich diagnostic feedback.

Currently deep learning is not by accumulating knowledge, but through using and applying knowledge as one engages in discipline-based activity (Harris Harris, Krajcik, Pellegrino & DeBarger, 2019). As such, those concerned with education policy and practice have shifted their

policy toward supporting deeper learning by emphasizing the importance of students' ability to apply knowledge in subject areas. However, designers of student's assessments have begun to follow suit and are taking up the challenge of creating a new generation of assessments with new types of tasks and situations that call upon students to demonstrate well integrated.

Machine learning is a subset of Artificial Intelligence (AI), it is a machine that can perform cognitive functions in a manner associated with the human's mind, such as problem-solving and learning. It can also be defined as the use of machines or computer to perform tasks that would typically require human intelligence (Gobbo & Pavan, 2022). In education, AI is used to develop and deliver personalized learning experiences, improve administrative efficiency and support teachers in decision-making processes. While, machine learning is a statistical process that helps to predict the output and future use of data. It is not only beneficial to students for this learning approach, but also save teachers great time from creating lesson plans that cater for students of all abilities and grade levels. It also shows automatic grading system that cannot be influenced by teacher-student-relationship.

Brief History of Machine Learning

In 1940s, based on the studies on the electrical crashes of the neurons, the scientists explained the decision-making mechanism of human by cannon and fire. In this way, the researches of the artificial intelligence started in the 1950s (Erdem, 2014). In those years, Alan Turin executed the Turing Test in order to test the ability of a machine to imitate a human. The aim of the Turing Test was to measure the ability of the machine to make a contact with a human during an interview. In 1956, the term 'artificial intelligence' was first used in a summer school held by Marvin Minsky from Massachusetts Institute of Technology, John McCarthy from Stanford University and Allen Newell and Herbert Simon from Carnegie-Mellon University. Until that time, Alan Turing's term, 'machine intelligence', had been used. In 1959, Arthur Samul created the checkers programme, and then machine learning got its way. From those developments to the 1980s, there were some studies on abstract mind, information-based systems, which was called the 'winter of artificial intelligence'. In the 1990s, artificial intelligence and machine learning studies accelerated due to the developments in game technologies. Some of the breakthrough areas in AI and machine Learning are Computer Vision, Natural Language Processing and Reinforcement Learning (Topal, 2017).

Within the field of Educational Assessment, there has been considerable improvement in the recent years. The evolution has been the result of technical progression associated with improvements in statistical methodology. The impulsive spread of the COVID-19 pandemic created a great significant impact in the lives of many across the nation. Teachers and students across the

elementary, secondary and tertiary institutions were constrained into a new teaching and learning environment. However, the technology advancement has not only to improve students across the traditional fundamental skills such as; cognitive domain, psychomotor domain and affective domain but also to enhance them in the rising constructs of 21st century skills. These key changes observed in the academic related literature to machine learning and assessment is based on experts input to adaptive learning, Predictive analytics learning, Personalized learning, automated feedback and counselling, and humanoid robots as assistants in university teaching (Buching, 2019). In adaptive learning, machine is gradually used to collect and analyze student learning data, outline learning styles and characteristics of each student, and then automatically adjust the teaching content, mode, to best suit their needs (Wu, 2019). Platform that integrates curriculum design, online learning, real-time feedback, adaptive learning, big data analysis, online collaborative learning, and intelligent coaching are designed for adaptive learning.

Machine learning is in the form of predictive analytics, it can draw conclusions about things that may happen in the future. For example, using a cumulative record data set of high school students, predictive analytics can tell us which ones are more likely to drop out due to academic failure or even their predicate score on a standardized test. It also supports personalized learning which could be used to provide each student with an individualized educational assessment and experience. Personalized learning is an educational model where students guide their own learning, go at their own pace, and in some cases make their own decisions about what to learn. Ideally, in a classroom that uses applications of data science, students choose what interests them and teachers adjust the curriculum and standards to the interests of the students. (Attaran, Stark, & Stotler, 2018; Ekowo & Palmer, 2016).

In the area of automated feedback and advice, early-warning systems, also called dropout systems, play an important role in identifying risk students. These systems use study history data to predict which students are at the risk of not successfully completing an examination or even an entire course. These students can then be warned and provided opportunities to work through their deficits. In this way, the success of studies can be improved, and students can be protected from failure (Arnold & Pistilli, 2012; Attaran, Stark, & Stotler, 2018). While development of humanoid robots to support teaching, directly interacts with students. Such robots can support teaching by asking questions or answering of questions (Büching et al., 2019). The United States, Australia, China and United Kingdom, institutions have already started to rely on various systems that support adaptive learning or individual performance feedback with the use of Machine learning applications and available relevant inventories (Ekowo & Palmer, 2016), but a systematic overview of the implementation of machine learning is not available in the educational policy in Nigeria University.

In terms of the future, trends of technological development at universities identified by an expert panel have widely impacted on how assessments can be plan and administered online. The traditional paper and pencil tests are becoming outdated as assessments are now being designed as adaptive and delivered online using interactive tasks and simulations (Gierl & Haladyna, 2012). This would call for the restructuring of learning spaces by considering mobility and flexibility development of blended learning formats, as well as collaborative learning in groups. In blended learning, the learning environment of the online room is opened. This simplifies access to learning content and improves flexibility. Simultaneously, opportunities are created for the use of multimedia and various other technology offerings (Adams et al., 2017).

Human & Machines

ML & AI

**Computer Based
Assessment (CBA)**

Figure 1: Trajectory Channel of Students' Computer-Based Assessment

The Trajectory Channel of Students' Computer-Based Assessment has been an explosion of new technology, improving from oral assessment to paper-and-pen that are slowly becoming outdated as now assessment is being designed as adaptive and delivered online using dynamic and interactive tasks and simulations (Luecht,2013). Computer-Based Assessment (CBA) is an assessment which is both delivered and marked by computer. It can be used for summative, formative or diagnostic unlike paper-based assessment. This improvement has led to Machine learning, a subset of Artificial Intelligence (AI). It is a machine that can perform cognitive functions in a manner associated with the human mind, such as problem-solving and learning. In education, AI is used to develop and deliver personalized learning experiences, improve administrative efficiency and support teachers in decision-making processes. It is not only beneficial to students for this learning approach, but also save teachers great time from creating

lesson plans that cater for students of all abilities and grade levels. It also shows automatic grading system that cannot be influenced by the teacher-student-relationship.

Types of Machine Learning

Machine Learning can be classified as follows;

1. Supervised learning
2. Unsupervised learning
3. Semi-supervised learning
4. Reinforced learning Supervised Learning

Supervised Learning: Supervised learning allows for predictions. The algorithm is given training data to use. There are two types of supervised learning: classification and regression supervised learning.

Classification: Distributing the data into the categories defined on the data set according to their specific features.

Regression: Predicting or concluding the other features of the data based on its some available features.

Unsupervised Learning: Unsupervised learning does not require prior training, and it can be used to find patterns even without previous information. The learning process occurs by using the relations and connections between the data. There are also two types of unsupervised learning: clustering and association.

Clustering: It finds the groupings of data which are similar to each other when an inherent grouping in the data is not known.

Association: Determines the relations and connections among the data in the same data set. Deduction of Features: In some cases, although lots of features about the data are known, the features related to group and category of the data cannot be determined. In such cases, selecting a subgroup of features or getting new features combining the features is called deduction of features (Erdem, 2014).

Semi-Supervised Learning: Semi-supervised learning is a middle ground between the supervised and unsupervised learning and it can increase the accuracy of predictions made by supervised learning algorithms. The difference between the semi-supervised learning and the supervised

learning is the labelled data set. In supervised learning, the labelled data are more than the data to be predicted. In contrast, in semi-supervised learning, the labelled data are less than the data to be predicted (Kızılkaya & Oguzlar, 2018).

Reinforcement Learning: Reinforcement learning is used for decision making, and the algorithm learns by receiving positive and negative feedback during a multi-step procedure. This is a kind of learning in which the agents learn via reward system.

Innovative Application in Machine Learning and Assessment

Several changes have taken place in term of machine learning and assessment. Some of these changes are as follows;

- (1) Adaptive learning
- (2) Predictive analytic learning
- (3) Personalized learning
- (4) Automated feedback and counselling
- (5) Automated evaluation of examination performance
- (6) Humanoid robots as assistants in university teaching

Adaptive Learning: Adaptive Learning (AL) refers to the use of technology and data to personalize and customize the learning experience for individual learners. It involves active adjusting the learning content, pace, and strategies based on the learner's needs and progress (Trushkina et al., 2020). The concept of adaptive learning is closely related to artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) techniques. AL systems gather data about the learner's performance, preferences, and behavior, and then use this information to make informed decisions about what and how to teach. In adaptive learning, machine is gradually used to collect and analyze student learning data, outline learning styles and characteristics of each student, and then automatically adjust the teaching content, mode, to best suit their needs (Wu, 2019). Platform that integrates curriculum design, online learning, real-time feedback, adaptive learning, big data analysis, online collaborative learning, and intelligent coaching are designed for adaptive learning. Teachers can use the tools and content library online platform to design courses, and each part of the teaching process can add elements of interaction with students, so that students can master the knowledge through completing some "tasks" in the course. Through these interactions, the system can collect student learning data at any time, track the progress of students, and discover the bottlenecks and difficulties of student learning, thus giving real-time feedback and reinforcement.

Lipton et al. (2018) recorded that the goal of adaptive learning is to optimize the learning process, improve learner engagement and motivation, and ultimately enhance learning outcomes. By tailoring the learning experience to individual learners, AL can accommodate different learning styles, preferences, and paces, allowing each learner to reach their full potential. It is important to note that adaptive learning is an evolving field, and advancements in AI and ML technologies continue to shape its development. As more data is collected and analyzed, and as algorithms become more sophisticated, adaptive learning systems are expected to become even more effective in providing personalized and engaging learning experiences.

Predictive Analytics Learning: Machine learning is in the form of predictive analytics that can draw conclusions about things that may happen in the future. For example, using a cumulative record data set of high school students, predictive analytics can tell us which ones are more likely to drop out due to academic failure or even their predicate score on a standardized test. (Adams et al., 2017; Sclater, Peasgood, & Mullan, 2016).

Personalized Learning: Predictive analytics can support personalized learning by supporting not only risk students but also their fellow students with adaptive and individually tailored learning offerings. In this way, the learning process is optimized and accelerated (Attaran, Stark, & Stotler, 2018; Ekowo & Palmer, 2016).

Automated Feedback and Counselling: It is also called dropout systems; it plays an important role in identifying risk of students. These systems use study history data to predict which students are at the risk of not successfully completing an examination or even an entire course. These students can then be warned and provided opportunities to work through their deficits. In this way, the success of studies can be improved, and students can be protected from failure (Arnold & Pistilli, 2012; Attaran, Stark, & Stotler, 2018).

Automated Evaluation of Examination Performance: Another potential application of predictive analytics at universities is automated evaluation of examination performance which uses so-called robot graders that is hybrids of robot graders and detection systems that can predict student performance in the form of grades are being pursued (Stark, & Stotler, 2018)

Humanoid Robots as assistants in University Teaching: The development of humanoid robots is to support teaching. These robots directly interact with students by asking questions or answering questions (Buching et al., 2019).

Benefits of Machine Learning

Advanced Evaluation and Grading: Machine learning technologies in education allows for smart assessments that can rapidly analyze many forms, including written assignments such as

papers, essays, and presentations. It also reduces assessment time to seconds, provide precise measurement of students' academic ability, and remove the possibility of human error.

Increased Learner Motivation: Online platforms enable learners to swiftly fill knowledge gaps and acquire critical skills by providing them with precisely what they need to achieve their learning objectives. Machine learning algorithms, monitor learner progress and update curricula and give students with personalized information

Increased Students' Efficiency: Machine learning has the ability to improve the organization and management of content and curriculum. It facilitates the work of teachers and students and makes them happy and comfortable with education which increases involvement and participation and learning

Speech Recognition: Machine learning helps speech recognition software to interpret voice input from consumers and other users. Virtual assistants on smartphones can be a good example of this. They understand voice inputs and requests from users, and then complete tasks using these inputs. It can be used for dictation programs, which allow people to make notes without having to type or write. This can be used for voice chat applications.

Fraud Detection: Machine learning algorithms are able to analyze spending and behaviour patterns in order to detect frauds such as insurance fraud and credit card fraud. These same analytical processes, pattern detection and security concerns can be used to identify scam messages.

Predictions that are more Accurate: Many businesses and policymakers are concerned about making accurate forecasts and predictions. This can include predictions about the stock exchange, the economy, and consumer preferences. Machine learning algorithms can identify patterns and trends using historical data to predict possible outcomes. The algorithm can then repeat this process using current data and make future predictions. The algorithm's ability to process and learn new data, as they arrive, allows it to improve over time.

Medical Diagnosis: Machine learning is useful in the health care sector for identifying those patients at risk of certain diseases. Machine learning algorithms use anonymous data from patient records to analyze patterns, combinations, and histories of lifestyle factors and symptoms in order to determine a person's risk for a specific condition. This can save medical professionals time by identifying at-risk individuals sooner and reducing the severity or the treatment required

Advertising and Marketing Works: Machine learning algorithms are able to predict which consumers will be most likely buy a particular product. Customer segmentation is a process that

Received: 23 January 2025

Revised: 02 February 2025

Accepted: 11 February 2025

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can be used to improve marketing and advertising campaigns. An algorithm could, for example, process huge amounts of data on consumers to determine who is most likely to buy a product if they are presented with advertising. The company can then send advertisements to the people who are most likely to respond positively to them and purchase.

Political Barrier to its Implementation in Educational Policy

The factors that contributed to the poor implementation of machine learning and assessment in Nigeria University are traceable to the barriers in educational policy formulation processes. The barriers are discussed as follows:

Digital Divide and Infrastructure Gaps

Nigeria faces significant challenges in terms of digital infrastructure, including inconsistent access to electricity and internet connectivity, particularly in rural areas. These infrastructure gaps exacerbate the digital divide, making the widespread implementation of ML-based assessments difficult. Political leaders are often reluctant to adopt policies that could further marginalize underprivileged students who lack access to necessary technological tools Oluwatobi, S. O., & Mebude, O. (2019).

Lack of Proper Strategy for Implementation

Strategy for education policy implementation is a vital stage in educational policy formulation. It is the planning stage that comes between policy formulation and implementation. According to Okoroma (2006), the problem of policy implementation is traceable to the planning stage which comes immediately after policy formulation. The National Policy on Education (NPE) is supposed to guide the operators of the system but it is short-sighted. It talks about the philosophy and objectives of Nigerian education at various levels but fails to proffer solution for the implementation by the classroom teachers and how the students would know when they have reached acceptable level of performance.

Lack of Political Will and Policy Framework

Nigeria has struggled with the development of a comprehensive policy framework for integrating advanced technologies like machine learning into education. Policymakers often prioritize traditional educational challenges such as improving access and quality over the implementation of newer technologies. This has resulted in limited strategic focus on education technology reforms and Machine learning-driven assessments Ekekwe, N. (2021). Again, the political environment has a strong influence on educational policy planning and implementation in any nation. Nigerian

Government has adopted education as a tool for national development (FRN, 2004). However, political will is the total political support policy by top government functionaries which our educational system in Nigeria has been lacking up till now; Why? Our leaders make promises that will never be fulfilled.

Lack of Continuity

The continue change in administrations which at the end lead to policy adjustment is considered as one of the major problems affecting policy implementation. This is because most programmes initiated by a particular administration are hardly completed by another administration after the termination of that government; the incoming government would come in with its own agenda. This constant change of education policy has been source of worry to teachers and it has caused havoc to the education sector because the changes are not often communicated to schools on time. (Vanguard Media, 2012).

Conclusion

Technology has influenced the objectives of assessment very significantly and meaningfully, in a way, not only to improve students across the traditional fundamental skills which are the cognitive domain, psychomotor domain and affective domain but also to enhance them in the rising constructs of 21st century skills. The evolution has been the result of a natural, technical progression associated with improvements in statistical methodology with adaptive learning, predictive analytic, personalized learning, automated feedback and humanoid robots as assistants in university teaching. But there are also clear barriers with evolving options for assessments that are adaptive and multi-staged in nature that utilize richer item format, response actions, media inclusions and interactivity. And also, game-based and virtual performance assessments that facilitate richer assessment opportunities should be implemented. Whilst machine learning and assessment is an emerging aspect of educational assessment, that yield rich diagnostic feedback, should be implemented in the National Policy on Education.

Suggestions

In view of the foregoing, the following suggestions were made:

1. Teachers should be incorporated as one of the major stakeholders for policy formulation and implementation of educational policy, since they are the ones that translate educational policy document into practice.
2. Since machine learning and assessment is an emerging aspect of educational assessment, that yield rich analytical feedback should be implemented in the educational policy in Nigeria

3. Government should build platform to assess a comprehensive range of skills, possibly; a national hub of educational assessment. This is because our educational system is not only to improve students' learning outcomes across the traditional fundamental skills but to enhance them in the emerging constructs of 21st century skills
4. Teachers should be trained in the use of machines, computer and online teaching and learning.

References

- Adams, B. S., Cummins, M., Davis, A., Freeman, A., Hall, G. C., & Ananthanarayanan, V. (2017). *NMC Horizon report; 2017 higher education*. Retrieved from <http://cdn.nmc.org/media/2017-nmc-horizon-report-he-en>.
- Arnold, K. E., & Pistilli, M. D. (2012). Course signals at purdue: Using learning analytics to Increase Student Success. 2nd international conference on learning analytics and knowledge. Vancouver, BC, Canada, 29th-May 2nd. New York.
- Attaran, M., Stark, J., & Stotler, D. (2018). Opportunities and challenges for big data analytic in US higher education: A conceptual model for implementation. *Industry and Higher Education*, 32(3), 169–182.
- Asuru, V. A., (2015). *Measurement and Evaluation in Education and psychology*. Pearl Publishers International Ltd. Port Harcourt.
- Buching, C., Mah, D.-K., Otto, S., Paulicke, P., & Hartmann, E. A. (2019). *Learning Analytics an Hochschulen*. In V. Wittpahl (Ed.), *Künstliche Intelligenz. Technologie, Anwendung, Gesellschaft* (142–160).
- Erdem, E. S. (2014). *Machine learning and its effect on student achievement in universities* Ankara Press
- Ekekwe, N. (2021). *The Challenges of Technology Adoption in Nigeria's Education Sector*. *The Nigerian Journal of Technology Policy*, 22(1), 15-30.
- Ekowo, M., & Palmer, I. (2016). *The promise and peril of predictive analytics in higher education. A landscape analysis*. Peril Publisher
- Ekowo, M., & Palmer, I. (2017). *Predictive analytics in higher education. Five guiding practices for ethical use*. Retrieved from <https://na-production.s3.amazonaws.com/documents/Predictive-Analytics-GuidingPractices.pdf>
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN) (2004). *National Policy on Education* (Revised): NERDC.

- Gierl, M. J., & Haladyna, T. M. (2012). Automatic item generation: An introduction. *In M. J. Gierl & T. M. Haladyna (Eds.), Automatic item generation: Theory and practice*, 3–12.
- Gierl, M. J., & Lai, H. (2012). Using item models for automatic item generation. *International Journal of Testing*, 12(4), 273–298.
- Harris, C. J., Krajcik, J. S., Pellegrino, J. W. & DeBarger, A. H. (2019). Designing knowledge in use assessments to promote deeper learning. *Educational Measurement, Issues and Practice*, 338(2), 53–67
- Luecht, R. M. (2013). Assessment engineering task model maps, task models and templates as a new way to develop and implement test specifications. *Journal of Applied Testing Technology*, 14(3), 1–15.
- Kızılkaya, Y. M. Oğuzlar, A. (2018). Machine learning, its benefit and disadvantages on education. *Journal of High Education Studies*, 37(3), 90-104.
- Madnani, N, Cahill, A. & Riordan, B. (2016). *Automatically scoring tests of proficiency in music instruction*, paper in proceedings of the 11th workshop on innovative use of NLP for building educational applications, 217–222
- Mao, L., Liu, O. L., Roohr, K., Belur, V., Mulholand, M, Lee, H-S & Pallant, A (2018). Validation of automated scoring for a formative assessment that employs scientific argumentation. *Journal of Educational Assessment*, 23(2), 121–138
- Nna-Kue, N. L & Anunaobi, J.C (2023). Classroom assessment, an integral part of teaching and learning in education. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*. 4(12), 5064-5071
- Oluwatobi, S. O., & Mebude, O. (2019). The Impact of Infrastructure Deficit on the Adoption of Educational Technology in Nigeria. *Journal of Educational and Instructional Studies in the World*, 9(2), 45-54
- Okoroma, N.S. (2006). An evaluation study of the 3-3 aspect of the national policy on Education in Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government areas of Rivers State', *Journal of Technical and Science Education*, 10(2), 45-59
- Riordan, B., Horbach, A., Cahill, A., Zesch, T. & Lee, C. M. (2017). *Investigating neural architectures for short answer scoring*, paper in proceedings of the 12th workshop on innovative use of NLP for building educational applications, 159–168.

- Sclater, N., & Mullan, J. (2017). *Briefing. learning analytics and student success – assessing the evidence. In Effective Learning Analytics.* Retrieved from http://repository.jisc.ac.uk/6560/1/learning-analytics_and_student_success.pdf
- Sclater, mN., Peasegood, A., & Mullan, J. (2016). *Learning analytics in higher education. A review of UK and international practice.* Retrieved from https://www.jisc.ac.uk/sites/default/files/learning-analytics-in-he-v2_0.pdf
- Sirmacek, B. (2020). The role of artificial intelligence in enhancing the educational process: A review of the literature. *Journal of Educational Technology Development and Exchange.* 15(1), 1-14.
- Topal, Ç. (2017). The impact of AI, machine learning, automation and robotics on the information professions. *Computer Assisted Language Learning*, 35(1), 1-15.
- Vanguard Media, (2012). *Confusion in education: 9-3-4, 6-3-3-4, 1-6-3-4, British, American or which curriculum.* Retrieve from: <http://www.vanguardngr.com.confusion-in-educationbritish-american-or-whichcurriculum>